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ABSTRACTS

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Isolation, characterisation and biocontrol potential of *Trichoderma* sp. isolated from rhizospheric soil of tomato

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Abstract: *Trichoderma* is a cosmopolitan fungus that represents efficient antagonistic and plant growth promoting activity. Tomato is one of the most important and common horticulture crops which is highly rich in vitamins. The crop is attacked by different types of pest and pathogens. *Ralstonia solanacearum* and *Botrytis cinerea* are two important bacterial and fungal pathogen of tomato. In the present study, *Trichoderma* sp. was isolated from rhizospheric soil of healthy tomato plant. The identification was made on the basis of morphological characteristic. Dual culture assay of *Trichoderma* against *Ralstonia solanacearum* and *Botrytis cinerea* was performed *in vitro*. *Trichoderma* sp. exhibited the highest mycelial inhibition rate (64.25 %) against *Botrytis cinerea*. The growth of *Ralstonia solanacearum* was inhibited by 63%. The fungus also showed good plant growth promoting (PGP) activity. Positive results were obtained for protease, cellulase, siderophore and IAA production. *In vitro* tests against plant phytopathogens indicate that the isolated strain of *Trichoderma* sp. is a promising option for development of biocontrol agent.

Keywords: *Trichoderma*, tomato, phytopathogens, *in vitro* assay, biocontrol, plant growth promotion

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